

KIAA1735/Dixin DIX domain containing 1 (DIXDC1) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

DIXDC1, when active, is known to stop cancer metastasis due to extreme stickiness, both in vitro and in vivo and it turns out to be inhibited in cancer and metastasis. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 DIXDC1 related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for DIXDC1-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) and Sobol indices, WNT3A

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr DIXDC1 comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

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1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of ${}^{71}C_3$ (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search done by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order DIXDC1 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination,

then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. KIAA1735/Dixin DIX domain containing 1 (DIXDC1)

Dishevelled DVL-1/2/3 are DIX-domain proteins implicated in the WNT signaling pathway. Katoh and Katoh [4] searched found an uncharacterized human KIAA1735 gene encoding a novel DIX-domain protein, using bioinformatics. They identified mouse ortholog of human KIAA1735 gene, and the nucleotide sequence of mouse KIAA1735 cDNA was determined in silico by assembling nucleotide sequences of ESTs BY753211, BQ931084, CA750490, BQ960056 and a 5'-truncated partial cDNA AK082960. Myosine-tail homologous (MTH) domain and C-terminal DIX domain were conserved between human KIAA1735 and mouse KIAA1735 proteins. A tyrosine phosphorylation site (Tyr 242) within the MTH domain was conserved between human KIAA1735 and mouse KIAA1735 proteins. KIAA1735 gene (consisting of 16 exons), was about 45 kb in size and on human chromosome 11q23.1, was located between D11S1391 and D11S1347 loci, the region deleted in sporadic breast cancer. This was the first report on comprehensive characterization of the KIAA1735 gene.

To become mobile, cancer cells usually override cellular machinery that keeps cells rooted within their respective locations. Deviously, cancer can switch on and off molecular anchors protruding from the cell membrane (called focal adhesion complexes), preparing the cell for migration. This allows cancer cells to begin the processes to traverse the body through the bloodstream and take up residence in new organs. Cancers missing polarization-related protein LKB1 or serine/threonine kinase 11 (Peutz-Jeghers syndrome) (LKB1/STK11) are often aggressive, rapidly spreading through the body. However, it was not known, how LKB1 and focal adhesions were connected. In an medical press release by the Salk Institute on July 17, 2014 in <https://medicalxpress.com/news/2014-07-gene-deadly-cancer.html#nR1v>, the Salk Institute team found the connection and a new target for therapy: DIXDC1. They discovered that DIXDC1 received instructions from LKB1 to go to focal adhesions and change their size and number. When DIXDC1 was active, focal adhesions grew large and sticky, anchoring cells to their spot, while when DIXDC1 was inactive, focal adhesions became small and numerous, resulting in hundreds of small hands that pull the cell forward in response to extracellular cues. That increased tendency to be mobile, aids in the escape from, for example, the lungs and allows tumor cells to survive travel through the bloodstream and dock at organs throughout the body. It turned out that DIXDC1 was inhibited in cancer and metastasis.

I present 3rd order combinations of DIXDC1 with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might

be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different time points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [5]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [5].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e

within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 DIXDC1-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [6]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [7] and martinez implementation in Martinez [8] and Baudin et al. [9]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested DIXDC1-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving DIXDC1 were obtained from a full set of ${}^71C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of GSK3-DIXDC1-X combinations

Martin et al. [10] propose that rare missense single-nucleotide variants (SNVs) in DIXDC1 contribute to psychiatric pathogenesis by reducing spine and glutamatergic synapse density downstream of GSK3 in the WNT/ β -catenin pathway. Looking at the

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
APC-DIXDC1-WNT2B	89	27000	33475	27891	27710	DIXDC1-NKD1-SEN2	139	26878	5252	13422	20937
DIXDC1-NKD1-TLE2	211	181	25309	23711	748	DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7L1	239	17174	2661	14197	5839
DIXDC1-FOXN1-FBXW4	330	3748	17556	12016	30746	DIXDC1-NKD1-PPP2CA	440	13162	40123	35144	6197
CCND1-CTBP1-DIXDC1	516	56574	53031	16545	48176	DIXDC1-PITX2-SEN2	526	28707	7274	5676	35235
DIXDC1-FOXN1-TLE2	581	740	1891	12323	28293	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD8	584	8409	1800	17070	5733
DIXDC1-PITX2-SFRP4	614	29602	6543	3868	43507	DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT4	690	39847	12582	10499	56262
DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1	777	45272	10940	6689	22555	DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT2	883	442	1751	18827	1642
DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	939	687	5376	7847	13303	DIXDC1-FZD2-LEF1	942	12211	3020	42787	29981
DIXDC1-LRP5-SEN2	1098	18807	1510	3942	4609	DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7L1	1100	22783	49446	23638	20089
DIXDC1-FGF4-FBXW4	1142	8123	30879	12840	50692	DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2	1148	28328	6949	7791	20834
DIXDC1-WNT3-WNT4	1279	51438	14477	19803	17251	DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4	1340	27624	17009	49472	50306
DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1	1397	18158	39442	41838	15514	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FRZB	1442	1877	4968	4749	2791
DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD8	1466	11545	29932	40243	14229	DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD7	1473	21462	19307	23718	22870
APC-DIXDC1-FRZB	1488	36338	55199	25861	797	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SEN2	1491	2077	4322	6058	1110
DIXDC1-PORCN-SEN2	1529	21963	6981	10680	50015	DIXDC1-FGF4-FRAT1	1533	9050	41138	51810	43824
DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT4	1536	13509	3143	4994	28564	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT4	1576	35367	3250	12254	41951
DIXDC1-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1	1609	31242	3865	16239	26807	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SEN2	1621	28519	557	27468	36407
DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1	1727	6226	28247	11263	35521	DIXDC1-NKD1-RHOU	1798	6195	3765	22405	3157
DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT5A	1830	5103	33835	49403	2232	DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1	1834	22981	29680	27665	50757
DIXDC1-FGF4-TLE2	1838	19948	33519	25723	52981	DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD8	1912	23178	24551	54089	31538
APC-DIXDC1-SFRP4	1940	34105	56875	25938	15956	APC-DIXDC1-DKK1	1973	39613	14672	51391	14145
DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1	2010	2457	38608	53030	25504	DIXDC1-FZD2-TLE2	2059	1052	41611	34129	44387
DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT4	2069	18260	5558	10405	1210	FZD5-DIXDC1-FRZB	2081	26083	51583	4776	41242
DIXDC1-LRP5-WNT4	2098	56736	1699	4505	8233	DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4	2128	13920	3978	2846	15403
DIXDC1-WNT1-WNT4	2134	8527	1926	11050	9192	DIXDC1-JUN-SEN2	2137	30487	37871	53712	15183
DIXDC1-NKD1-PPP2R1A	2140	5484	54992	25998	568	DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD1	2148	34299	35191	38859	49381
DIXDC1-FZD2-FBXW4	2156	27392	32655	28804	43752	DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT4	2177	45494	1826	20781	48238
DIXDC1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	2235	15861	11040	56361	22586	DIXDC1-JUN-TLE2	2288	253	494	55465	49628
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT2	2324	510	6244	12086	918	DIXDC1-PORCN-FBXW4	2360	25666	16237	7265	54640
DIXDC1-TLE1-TLE2	2398	24851	22502	52222	23488	DIXDC1-JUN-WNT2	2424	1633	23267	35271	23259
DIXDC1-FZD2-LRP5	2550	15903	14969	51496	19500	CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-WNT2B	2602	9079	34225	44850	51306
FZD5-DIXDC1-SEN2	2634	37000	48018	1887	44271	DIXDC1-FGF4-SEN2	2635	18261	53316	27142	35362
APC-DIXDC1-TCF7L1	2672	33791	54110	6164	16187	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	2673	40171	11882	42208	52840
DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7	2704	16324	46726	24262	6288	DIXDC1-SFRP1-WNT4	2827	56975	50212	3166	44324
DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT2B	2863	14619	3889	45440	40568	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	2905	17149	580	6704	6648
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-SEN2	2907	45126	54761	32938	29362	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SFRP4	3011	7186	9197	19775	49994
DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7L1	3076	32005	36386	8205	35936	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2B	3115	8791	13513	44897	31757
DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2	3118	7736	11350	8945	27577	DIXDC1-FZD2-SFRP4	3134	5020	36408	6731	42615
DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1	3136	45375	11211	11425	29794	DIXDC1-PORCN-TLE2	3192	8903	21007	23935	55707
DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	3193	33168	18183	17378	30931	DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT4	3214	52681	19702	7189	37575
FZD5-DIXDC1-WNT2B	3222	37056	32234	42255	42076	DIXDC1-FOXN1-PPP2CA	3235	4976	13715	8671	2172
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-RHOU	3247	13611	55894	17887	29476	DIXDC1-FSHB-T	3255	34040	47003	6560	49035
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT2B	3266	11238	38406	37800	51881	DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1	3310	15749	16154	12064	34806
DIXDC1-JUN-RHOU	3325	2215	36161	42538	1991	DIXDC1-FOXN1-LEF1	3327	3173	8059	15927	10884
DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3347	13841	2607	50326	30275	DIXDC1-SFRP1-FBXW4	3348	22994	35667	16096	50638
DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7	3385	34777	40983	22775	42381	APC-DIXDC1-FBXW2	3395	2911	34269	1471	6570
DIXDC1-EP300-FBXW11	3401	6056	10476	24069	55750	DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT5A	3402	30477	40511	46509	49117
DIXDC1-SFRP1-TCF7	3404	44931	42751	37910	31320	DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4	3436	6471	26909	5680	17650
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-DKK1	3474	22358	26349	38523	54006	DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT2	3514	7982	20770	47082	45891
FZD5-CCND3-DIXDC1	3536	349	4283	26959	12747	DIXDC1-JUN-WNT3A	3551	836	21850	41587	6942
DIXDC1-FZD2-PPP2CA	3662	17928	10686	40372	29250	DIXDC1-GSK3A-RHOU	3688	25193	1738	30131	17732
DIXDC1-FZD6-FZD8	3726	30855	3487	51102	3333	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SFRP4	3785	1242	4939	11642	2468
DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD1	3799	13273	8362	12714	28800	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD7	3818	4807	3291	13093	46632
DIXDC1-FGF4-SLC9A3R1	3858	41464	33881	21954	50193	DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT5A	3863	7743	18318	21775	11741
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT5A	3885	26867	8379	47688	52084	DIXDC1-NKD1-WIF1	3909	12873	22358	12920	23739
DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT4	4006	46441	40742	22331	52314	DIXDC1-PORCN-RHOU	4036	27252	7449	17205	39479
DIXDC1-GSK3A-TCF7L1	4067	26243	14041	22033	41642	DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2B	4120	780	1909	4603	6598
DIXDC1-PITX2-PPP2CA	4123	13781	1911	14325	45522	DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7	4146	31420	19458	30214	27951
DIXDC1-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	4147	35870	12879	23397	50086	DIXDC1-FOXN1-LRP6	4184	4399	11080	16729	11346
DIXDC1-DVL2-FOSL1	4189	23516	3806	16734	50139	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2	4199	3075	55905	23835	33613
DIXDC1-FGF4-LRP5	4209	32587	26371	42858	41494	DIXDC1-FOXN1-PPP2R1A	4318	4042	7718	10315	5136
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-FRZB	4374	20252	52588	28893	38695	APC-DIXDC1-FOSL1	4389	42880	52076	6079	13090
DIXDC1-JUN-TLE1	4454	18781	16283	26133	14897	DIXDC1-GSK3A-TLE2	4469	19803	48789	49172	55138

Table 1: Rankings of DIXDC1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of GSK family along with DIXDC1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DIXDC1-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1, DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1, DIXDC1-GSK3A-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-GSK3A-SEN2, DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT4, DIXDC1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1, DIXDC1-GSK3A-SFRP4,

RANKING @ t_1 USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
APC-DIXDC1-WNT2B	33671	16882	4145	48106	51792	DIXDC1-NKD1-SEN2	24325	22750	54264	38554	4248
DIXDC1-NKD1-TLE2	22103	8452	55942	25492	11873	DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7L1	32308	45794	57018	24322	3679
DIXDC1-FOXN1-FBXW4	3530	9085	27138	3878	80	DIXDC1-NKD1-PPP2CA	9807	43231	37477	30170	1078
CCND1-CTBP1-DIXDC1	43082	54629	13851	25493	5299	DIXDC1-PITX2-SEN2	3537	43865	15972	13329	19669
DIXDC1-FOXN1-TLE2	1845	16001	48828	19868	1211	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD8	2700	34651	54623	33036	17361
DIXDC1-PITX2-SFRP4	9005	33898	35036	1595	29334	DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT4	25202	25146	26100	53862	33842
DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1	56469	45507	52727	16153	8570	DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT2	30452	9192	55932	6605	10010
DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	3184	5794	52693	37317	689	DIXDC1-FZD2-LEF1	35664	4924	22855	3469	6648
DIXDC1-LRP5-SEN2	1777	23484	44827	123	12925	DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7L1	22093	37245	28474	19140	2863
DIXDC1-FGF4-FBXW4	863	8394	9981	4999	2166	DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2	11918	40028	27691	41589	5926
DIXDC1-WNT3-WNT4	23687	55063	42305	53552	6689	DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4	53699	39669	27414	16988	3729
DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1	36423	32144	31736	45585	462	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FRZB	2525	19420	51785	5266	224
DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD8	12238	10132	30096	29586	5638	DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD7	20526	11029	56170	887	16741
APC-DIXDC1-FRZB	10225	33713	18843	30318	48974	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SEN2	1565	39282	50555	4197	2183
DIXDC1-PORCN-SEN2	16346	39480	19973	18502	14705	DIXDC1-FGF4-FRAT1	2503	5561	19946	26820	16773
DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT4	28297	20930	51455	19765	821	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT4	16200	33727	42194	2888	3723
DIXDC1-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1	40658	33882	42168	6416	5904	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SEN2	407	29880	52868	49762	5769
DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1	14683	17223	32337	21120	1723	DIXDC1-NKD1-RHOU	22817	19488	48855	52946	7640
DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT5A	50477	15744	20410	52735	35648	DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1	2494	21424	29421	5565	13873
DIXDC1-FGF4-TLE2	483	5164	27361	31117	107	DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD8	298	43502	31467	49346	4208
APC-DIXDC1-SFRP4	35041	36541	11687	4001	53042	APC-DIXDC1-DKK1	15397	35669	351	47431	19313
DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1	28857	3	41815	56574	3054	DIXDC1-FZD2-TLE2	27650	769	44018	38166	114
DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT4	3943	26131	55172	7688	2054	FZD5-DIXDC1-FRZB	7782	18262	19011	49028	55000
DIXDC1-LRP5-WNT4	7502	57090	41500	5927	3494	DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4	5010	8900	42377	1999	3181
DIXDC1-WNT1-WNT4	8940	3055	44478	355	3113	DIXDC1-JUN-SEN2	14743	34149	32447	35142	1484
DIXDC1-NKD1-PPP2R1A	41282	2633	37452	52221	22216	DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD1	747	28163	2771	16612	5332
DIXDC1-FZD2-FBXW4	10826	17817	13933	14350	2675	DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT4	1408	54188	56943	11999	14706
DIXDC1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	52675	33774	46150	40855	4391	DIXDC1-JUN-TLE2	20372	1335	37154	33910	5318
DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2	4715	14636	41748	5	92	DIXDC1-PORCN-FBXW4	17443	35486	7874	10595	38652
DIXDC1-TLE1-TLE2	47116	48849	22114	26437	1356	DIXDC1-JUN-WNT2	54748	2832	42019	31686	7633
DIXDC1-FZD2-LRP5	38335	7398	15968	15952	6915	CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-WNT2B	56105	5718	34204	36658	46240
FZD5-DIXDC1-SEN2	7671	36100	18300	18941	42529	DIXDC1-FGF4-SEN2	160	19260	11857	32192	2906
APC-DIXDC1-TCF7L1	12380	40622	3158	36294	44580	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	2313	39361	52671	23807	16817
DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7	22420	28291	44348	38473	4381	DIXDC1-SFRP1-WNT4	33874	55995	36243	38745	9587
DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT2B	12649	21037	9654	4112	8993	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	5496	29137	51814	26182	1076
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-SEN2	37857	43110	9454	11888	27966	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SFRP4	1515	4288	53430	32178	8501
DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7L1	651	50224	24155	46787	4158	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2B	29750	42429	10691	1083	508
DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2	9260	4892	51202	277	17819	DIXDC1-FZD2-SFRP4	12606	2707	46976	3589	4712
DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1	3527	44586	55840	4528	2895	DIXDC1-PORCN-TLE2	19616	669	29894	3284	37516
DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	9179	35935	48383	28960	14143	DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT4	11062	47027	42885	4269	14148
FZD5-DIXDC1-WNT2B	23182	22191	7617	31293	49776	DIXDC1-FOXN1-PPP2CA	1796	26077	33448	2622	1308
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-RHOU	49459	11518	16506	41618	49774	DIXDC1-FSHB-T	36455	36262	54691	1183	12572
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT2B	20111	15273	9550	18377	30375	DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1	34751	15623	55443	44289	5640
DIXDC1-JUN-RHOU	18846	1396	22896	56027	5582	DIXDC1-FOXN1-LEF1	4484	22384	44563	30946	6976
DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	962	5165	52201	49330	13895	DIXDC1-SFRP1-FBXW4	45118	28237	10152	6125	20898
DIXDC1-PITX2-TCF7	212	40331	3449	35829	42516	APC-DIXDC1-FBXW2	10263	2964	14162	56148	46075
DIXDC1-EP300-FBXW11	24668	2475	1975	54678	8438	DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT5A	4107	43702	11521	38540	15389
DIXDC1-SFRP1-TCF7	8030	45487	21797	52378	10376	DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4	25837	3880	29684	25017	18802
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-DKK1	26769	29764	1454	44361	36145	DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT2	6700	15468	53440	14555	7349
FZD5-CCND3-DIXDC1	11879	28312	52076	14071	46337	DIXDC1-JUN-WNT3A	26524	53	54094	51456	1811
DIXDC1-FZD2-PPP2CA	8902	30326	5894	8118	11004	DIXDC1-GSK3A-RHOU	1189	22635	55336	44689	20684
DIXDC1-FZD6-FZD8	49470	13675	53674	51243	47473	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SFRP4	3331	12759	51727	22386	2313
DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD1	1993	16416	32872	56	73	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD7	4124	10434	48541	5064	21094
DIXDC1-FGF4-SLC9A3R1	5138	30311	47799	27456	9771	DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT5A	5575	34443	41139	40268	26945
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT5A	17412	29192	9192	10144	42283	DIXDC1-NKD1-WIF1	44180	9421	57087	48747	10766
DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT4	313	50493	39435	43390	15890	DIXDC1-PORCN-RHOU	12463	7504	10181	47443	33854
DIXDC1-GSK3A-TCF7L1	1618	40131	51849	34033	22311	DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2B	4897	28389	42117	706	3398
DIXDC1-PITX2-PPP2CA	5166	50281	13595	5982	18374	DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7	10913	27332	15382	32534	9573
DIXDC1-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	29598	31337	32266	1590	25940	DIXDC1-FOXN1-LRP6	11784	23013	33845	22671	7286
DIXDC1-DVL2-FOSL1	43944	24373	54411	4440	3516	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2	20495	10746	26583	29184	3097
DIXDC1-FGF4-LRP5	2094	38170	10348	51983	7277	DIXDC1-FOXN1-PPP2R1A	3585	17552	18249	8440	13079
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-FRZB	40009	20796	7792	3587	52750	APC-DIXDC1-FOSL1	29898	50944	4006	7452	38509
DIXDC1-JUN-TLE1	38829	51316	25565	40475	1022	DIXDC1-GSK3A-TLE2	619	4353	47970	38190	7644

Table 2: Rankings of DIXDC1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT2, DIXDC1-GSK3A-RHOU and DIXDC1-GSK3A-TLE2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

RANKING @ t_1 USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
APC-DIXDC1-WNT2B	32686	46138	57032	49706	8604	DIXDC1-NKD1-SEN2	12200	40063	24628	25782	18022
DIXDC1-NKD1-TLE2	43632	33173	40815	48692	18613	DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7L1	55683	3768	38514	52231	4444
DIXDC1-FOXN1-FBXW4	3908	42858	13043	142	51587	DIXDC1-NKD1-PPP2CA	13275	33550	23785	28183	10803
CCND1-CTBPI-DIXDC1	51559	45701	51922	55396	12393	DIXDC1-PITX2-SEN2	55978	6920	46363	55209	16814
DIXDC1-FOXN1-TLE2	862	48313	19636	847	30685	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD8	1805	11167	25446	13189	38746
DIXDC1-PITX2-SFRP4	46369	10535	43650	52909	13347	DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT4	52700	17940	45762	56841	2056
DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1	48274	9621	43078	41675	11440	DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT2	2739	39551	16389	12555	40067
DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	21482	50446	17603	1664	40258	DIXDC1-FZD2-LEF1	1088	23042	12774	26014	35884
DIXDC1-LRP5-SEN2	4268	28488	25270	8378	13292	DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7L1	56033	13065	46115	48353	32433
DIXDC1-FGF4-FBXW4	55336	3744	38325	50113	22659	DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2	6691	25178	18767	17941	39342
DIXDC1-WNT3-WNT4	46662	7426	56710	34574	35761	DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4	23517	23502	15073	18409	44877
DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1	9143	45568	15142	2009	35636	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FRZB	7469	45639	21161	7194	29894
DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD8	56260	17140	40677	41871	25346	DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD7	897	39906	16491	15323	31948
APC-DIXDC1-FRZB	31034	40280	35412	35124	5166	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SEN2	49092	3697	41057	55136	27309
DIXDC1-PORCN-SEN2	34245	4241	41483	50058	10738	DIXDC1-FGF4-FRAT1	2172	8556	22888	20956	35669
DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT4	4313	56293	22786	21278	56181	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT4	230	13998	10061	1865	31112
DIXDC1-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1	234	54581	21361	4437	35419	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SEN2	4187	45495	18577	15069	48321
DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1	37975	14894	44042	43100	25518	DIXDC1-NKD1-RHO	51754	30025	31933	35781	48497
DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT5A	52842	853	34383	35927	975	DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1	3396	43706	23582	7101	52388
DIXDC1-FGF4-TLE2	54285	6424	40061	52770	29144	DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD8	40380	33429	31354	35470	16312
APC-DIXDC1-SFRP4	15501	36469	4573	12207	49027	APC-DIXDC1-DKK1	28809	54348	55519	53961	4157
DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1	460	53163	11120	19183	46244	DIXDC1-FZD2-TLE2	44992	16577	34379	33577	22179
DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT4	56220	46188	42283	53911	12529	FZD5-DIXDC1-FRZB	51905	1632	56983	53968	5137
DIXDC1-LRP5-WNT4	22389	29687	26166	18602	8466	DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4	16250	51618	16235	15399	35237
DIXDC1-WNT1-WNT4	45923	10872	37922	33117	17030	DIXDC1-JUN-SEN2	38065	7371	44233	41749	19679
DIXDC1-NKD1-PPP2R1A	43958	23448	33394	28989	46225	DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD1	44874	43035	30939	38627	8168
DIXDC1-FZD2-FBXW4	56232	25918	42123	46272	12936	DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT4	1153	10495	17804	9290	36662
DIXDC1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	33623	33561	42103	38759	12207	DIXDC1-JUN-TLE2	7892	39524	19988	13521	40054
DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2	43535	35529	42565	47624	18417	DIXDC1-PORCN-FBXW4	1721	49990	10280	3777	54067
DIXDC1-TLE1-TLE2	45671	17341	43136	37364	19250	DIXDC1-JUN-WNT2	56245	48642	40270	46652	20598
DIXDC1-FZD2-LRP5	56074	33993	44384	31111	21236	CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-WNT2B	12114	7749	26029	14404	44639
FZD5-DIXDC1-SEN2	12548	45142	1799	1150	54604	DIXDC1-FGF4-SEN2	454	43789	15313	3448	36983
APC-DIXDC1-TCF7L1	38058	40213	34148	43547	5611	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	9860	10843	21802	13865	42962
DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7	1474	53318	18628	4936	52772	DIXDC1-SFRP1-WNT4	182	13057	19225	8756	34550
DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT2B	3174	55687	15258	13757	29932	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	53240	14302	44216	57016	5570
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-SEN2	41101	55342	49465	39012	8801	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SFRP4	945	4750	12057	2266	34917
DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7L1	50862	18674	31836	42480	10593	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2B	56478	39042	43251	43795	29912
DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2	38631	6548	43841	56224	38207	DIXDC1-FZD2-SFRP4	921	31332	15052	10925	44257
DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1	26998	49234	15449	5156	42294	DIXDC1-PORCN-TLE2	8703	44992	26681	8337	53434
DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	2188	42426	19263	4130	25766	DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT4	44341	8459	33406	35610	21988
FZD5-DIXDC1-WNT2B	54948	13222	54779	55520	8127	DIXDC1-FOXN1-PPP2CA	55813	13913	43667	51754	13189
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-RHO	16058	1799	7780	18030	48278	DIXDC1-FSHB-T	13832	55402	22848	25333	31832
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT2B	3373	21084	13572	18388	49569	DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1	1757	23783	11410	15776	43723
DIXDC1-JUN-RHO	19039	49606	12978	15409	37376	DIXDC1-FOXN1-LEF1	35678	6740	39623	55489	17084
DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	56097	50759	42458	41643	27236	DIXDC1-SFRP1-FBXW4	55949	41407	41264	47501	25268
DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7	6315	38617	25338	14741	46743	APC-DIXDC1-FBXW2	14383	8045	12142	11236	52411
DIXDC1-EP300-FBXW11	16478	41314	19565	26955	35640	DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT5A	54426	18498	38052	43829	24212
DIXDC1-SFRP1-TCF7	890	1914	16315	5621	27382	DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4	54866	7550	40448	43753	13270
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-DKK1	5009	2538	5529	18100	16388	DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT2	597	7535	13277	13073	47490
FZD5-CCND3-DIXDC1	3555	36661	15848	15568	15517	DIXDC1-JUN-WNT3A	642	31777	12679	15634	45593
DIXDC1-FZD2-PPP2CA	5808	37464	22448	10828	35992	DIXDC1-GSK3A-RHO	54644	35360	40518	47979	9311
DIXDC1-FZD6-FZD8	56956	15247	44176	49716	7398	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SFRP4	53999	36905	42015	41308	11320
DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD1	1478	52928	13983	8965	23821	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD7	50549	11423	33617	36938	24059
DIXDC1-FGF4-SLC9A3R1	803	49054	15124	7558	23915	DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT5A	7919	48369	15784	27764	27632
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT5A	952	7968	6431	9090	46718	DIXDC1-NKD1-WIF1	2783	6193	1919	15666	44738
DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT4	2727	38766	19126	13360	32955	DIXDC1-PORCN-RHO	22917	52952	15739	7094	46487
DIXDC1-GSK3A-TCF7L1	55304	4458	37900	47670	20477	DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2B	12833	46485	21688	21438	30822
DIXDC1-PITX2-PPP2CA	53041	37364	46121	33605	10550	DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7	1127	43943	11040	8787	25066
DIXDC1-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	55438	7194	46909	53393	3075	DIXDC1-FOXN1-LRP6	55653	44861	40676	56911	28411
DIXDC1-DVL2-FOSL1	13850	26222	9929	15760	22430	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2	674	18194	13987	13381	27396
DIXDC1-FGF4-LRP5	50687	4628	32622	28888	25725	DIXDC1-FOXN1-PPP2R1A	6911	39828	26802	5793	42038
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-FRZB	9906	50249	14891	20119	39408	APC-DIXDC1-FOSL1	20176	3680	12346	13612	45427
DIXDC1-JUN-TLE1	47964	11280	42049	55138	21421	DIXDC1-GSK3A-TLE2	44093	27389	37086	47589	18303

Table 3: Rankings of DIXDC1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of CCND-DIXDC1-X combinations

DIXDC1 is the human homolog of Coiled-coil0-DIX1 (CCD1), a recently identified DIX domain containing protein in zebrafish. It is a positive regulator in the WNT signaling pathway functioning downstream of WNT and upstream of AXIN. Wang et al.

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
APC-DIXDC1-WNT2B	33667	9816	37410	33932	21947	DIXDC1-NKD1-SEN2	6022	11818	20358	22850	47306
DIXDC1-NKD1-TLE2	6700	20026	2140	33064	56018	DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7L1	29646	5112	10423	27152	45909
DIXDC1-FOXN1-FBXW4	268	9366	30340	20615	51974	DIXDC1-NKD1-PPP2CA	5108	14247	10722	14891	52539
CCND1-CTBP1-DIXDC1	39233	51733	37467	4117	18364	DIXDC1-PITX2-SEN2	22480	35744	10230	30579	35447
DIXDC1-FOXN1-TLE2	36166	9638	12945	39505	51979	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD8	1511	18357	6077	28359	49589
DIXDC1-PITX2-SFRP4	6126	5499	2542	31975	46995	DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT4	12247	40184	4921	27175	55522
DIXDC1-FSHB-LEF1	36469	12003	5172	34968	35203	DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT2	41110	34517	15046	10924	44951
DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	11078	11553	5133	32051	21036	DIXDC1-FZD2-LEF1	51813	25841	40535	5106	32449
DIXDC1-LRP5-SEN2	11654	7229	13083	25007	48199	DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7L1	10687	33985	3856	944	34060
DIXDC1-FGF4-FBXW4	28018	12698	1475	26671	40652	DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2	27322	44564	29539	36845	42568
DIXDC1-WNT3-WNT4	7590	21662	40072	54760	19415	DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4	4436	32111	14584	49771	47714
DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1	217	3466	4432	50780	14710	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FRZB	951	47159	3603	6086	38758
DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD8	17450	38369	2959	42245	39339	DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD7	48358	19451	28060	6775	28056
APC-DIXDC1-FRZB	33115	51649	4357	37198	37780	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SEN2	12650	15173	6381	13084	40680
DIXDC1-PORCN-SEN2	6264	29786	2478	31653	56322	DIXDC1-FGF4-FRAT1	11311	3948	23704	36266	46313
DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT4	46229	42232	4694	26610	37481	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT4	50281	20232	28903	8355	45251
DIXDC1-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1	4153	54566	52591	20026	22816	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SEN2	4657	10192	39345	33463	52455
DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1	5296	33823	22412	27612	28817	DIXDC1-NKD1-RHOU	35301	33949	301	25928	32354
DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT5A	15090	51048	5734	37333	37533	DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1	54614	11564	51051	37580	52640
DIXDC1-FGF4-TLE2	22985	5061	3232	32484	49190	DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD8	7499	42196	8744	33348	24458
APC-DIXDC1-SFRP4	44004	8828	20959	18701	42898	APC-DIXDC1-DKK1	15162	17237	32998	34401	34895
DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1	48918	4343	12297	8429	46878	DIXDC1-FZD2-TLE2	7517	35131	15931	19006	38624
DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT4	32682	1731	13063	29733	30817	FZD5-DIXDC1-FRZB	55273	45019	31156	2772	15403
DIXDC1-LRP5-WNT4	1097	14539	41487	34988	44516	DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4	1935	7729	30708	20858	4426
DIXDC1-WNT1-WNT4	31540	9049	855	15412	43794	DIXDC1-JUN-SEN2	5000	8754	23578	24410	21985
DIXDC1-NKD1-PPP2R1A	12774	34350	23086	9498	28407	DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD1	10865	24980	35542	34691	47440
DIXDC1-FZD2-FBXW4	12502	51956	8267	18466	41111	DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT4	33583	29470	10959	48219	48401
DIXDC1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	5241	2060	20905	18657	38375	DIXDC1-JUN-TLE2	53807	6763	10241	43682	13530
DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2	7403	52662	1657	22206	26879	DIXDC1-PORCN-FBXW4	30581	27114	17569	26399	20501
DIXDC1-TLE1-TLE2	16292	26653	1769	14067	20107	DIXDC1-JUN-WNT2	18889	10636	2095	27342	34026
DIXDC1-FZD2-LRP5	10699	40879	3704	571	41523	CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-WNT2B	40930	25751	23698	20111	41840
FZD5-DIXDC1-SEN2	8601	463	8415	11540	54865	DIXDC1-FGF4-SEN2	46104	5390	2470	34179	42901
APC-DIXDC1-TCF7L1	41920	36449	5777	31508	45652	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	29130	17039	31425	43932	47844
DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7	22606	17292	25852	24237	19475	DIXDC1-SFRP1-WNT4	5295	28151	32604	54855	40585
DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT2B	1930	455	20150	24837	6597	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	13747	36731	1621	19791	44841
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-SEN2	20044	11521	45187	29174	46555	DIXDC1-GSK3A-SFRP4	5734	9389	15081	44675	50176
DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7L1	12007	30185	796	27300	24504	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2B	22867	9461	1640	16526	47355
DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2	5303	19804	36529	40903	23672	DIXDC1-FZD2-SFRP4	21290	41685	6065	19346	48800
DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1	26861	25469	5480	18666	9251	DIXDC1-PORCN-TLE2	24570	31030	4033	26538	38066
DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	31758	28937	44898	49405	29636	DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT4	7785	53066	8449	29987	33965
FZD5-DIXDC1-WNT2B	45557	55783	27621	24453	55581	DIXDC1-FOXN1-PPP2CA	35953	3598	11243	27761	42557
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-RHOU	37350	50752	24433	17248	3736	DIXDC1-FSHB-T	314	15562	3544	12886	50313
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT2B	1674	21335	11428	19858	16898	DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1	20065	1974	41063	55571	41726
DIXDC1-JUN-RHOU	1538	5511	26896	46805	23218	DIXDC1-FOXN1-LEF1	7023	27219	3793	26174	55411
DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	34532	265	13430	34486	30125	DIXDC1-SFRP1-FBXW4	16701	3536	47910	19490	31678
DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7	17499	15060	14991	19767	54462	APC-DIXDC1-FBXW2	48601	593	9339	25447	50548
DIXDC1-EP300-FBXW11	22658	1104	15939	45977	30698	DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT5A	21879	5576	19569	19900	43009
DIXDC1-SFRP1-TCF7	1089	8252	34267	45557	39729	DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4	22603	4145	2181	34664	55633
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-DKK1	32455	51113	13061	32408	39336	DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT2	2995	10180	28312	47873	50919
FZD5-CCND3-DIXDC1	34974	54378	55279	47196	4169	DIXDC1-JUN-WNT3A	10815	54602	4233	32407	48637
DIXDC1-FZD2-PPP2CA	54976	12173	19646	34326	33129	DIXDC1-GSK3A-RHOU	23620	13806	30840	17745	26120
DIXDC1-FZD6-FZD8	39475	32326	5040	35193	34707	DIXDC1-FOXN1-SFRP4	19463	8158	30816	2260	33075
DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD1	750	787	14926	4990	44787	DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD7	11175	45761	11175	45761	43928
DIXDC1-FGF4-SLC9A3R1	44312	3067	8895	28067	45819	DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT5A	1445	8496	13536	21503	49118
DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT5A	16164	11219	7718	36336	22820	DIXDC1-NKD1-WIF1	25261	12692	13277	18270	29788
DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT4	39686	11178	11859	27866	48814	DIXDC1-PORCN-RHOU	8451	16024	6838	16323	15225
DIXDC1-GSK3A-TCF7L1	13617	4253	31101	36532	35765	DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2B	152	7787	3550	26021	52846
DIXDC1-PITX2-PPP2CA	13451	49710	9306	15472	45623	DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7	25114	2799	26209	719	32899
DIXDC1-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	25849	7370	2556	34488	39591	DIXDC1-FOXN1-LRP6	31357	1834	1266	20943	35723
DIXDC1-DVL2-FOSL1	6809	2410	30482	55232	50365	DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2	23829	19932	30211	4948	6868
DIXDC1-FGF4-LRP5	14168	25687	31151	12530	42935	DIXDC1-FOXN1-PPP2R1A	17025	25373	2795	32623	47876
CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-FRZB	41849	47252	26901	9551	7388	APC-DIXDC1-FOSL1	36431	3468	3305	21169	43364
DIXDC1-JUN-TLE1	5888	1931	2438	23064	47099	DIXDC1-GSK3A-TLE2	7443	38685	3609	36382	23060

Table 4: Rankings of DIXDC1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

[11] examined the biological role of DIXDC1 in human colon cancer and found that up-regulation of DIXDC1 protein was detected in human colorectal adenocarcinoma tissues and was found to be correlated well with high cell proliferation index. They also showed that DIXDC1 promoted G0/G1 to S phase transition concomitantly with

up-regulation of CCND1 and down-regulation of p21 protein. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of CCND family along with DIXDC1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CCND1-CTBP1-DIXDC1 and FZD5-CCND3-DIXDC1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of TCF-DIXDC1-X combinations

Wang et al. [12] provide the first evidence that long form (l-DIXDC1) may act as a novel branching component in the WNT signaling pathway targeting both β -catenin-TCF complex for gene expression and cytoskeleton for regulating dynamics of actin filaments. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of TCF family along with DIXDC1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1, APC-DIXDC1-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7, DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-FGF4-TCF7, DIXDC1-SFRP1-TCF7, DIXDC1-GSK3A-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-NKD1-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7L1 and DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of WNT-DIXDC1-X combinations

Wang et al. [13] showed that the DIXDC1 protein was induced upon WNT3A stimulation, whereas the DIXDC1 mRNA level was not significantly increased after WNT3A treatment. They detected positive DIXDC1 staining in colon cancer cells and colocalization with β -catenin staining. Their further investigation showed that the DIXDC1 protein was degraded through the proteasome pathway, and the activation of canonical Wnt signaling decreased the ubiquitin-dependent degradation of both the ectopic and endogenous DIXDC1 protein. In order to explore the possible mechanism of the ubiquitination of DIXDC1, they found that the phosphorylation of DIXDC1 was inhibited by WNT3A. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of WNT family along with DIXDC1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - APC-DIXDC1-WNT2B, DIXDC1-WNT3-WNT4, DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT4, DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT5A, DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT4, DIXDC1-LRP5-WNT4, DIXDC1-WNT1-WNT4, DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2, DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT2B, DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2, DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT2B, DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT5A, DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT4, DIXDC1-PORCN-WNT4, DIXDC1-NKD1-WNT2, DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT4, DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4, DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT4, DIXDC1-JUN-WNT2, CSNK1G1-DIXDC1-WNT2B, DIXDC1-SFRP1-WNT4, DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2B, DIXDC1-PITX2-WNT4, DIXDC1-FGF4-WNT5A, DIXDC1-GSK3A-WNT2, DIXDC1-JUN-WNT3A, DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT5A, DIXDC1-FOXN1-WNT2B and DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.5. Examining the behaviour of FZD-DIXDC1-X combinations

All three WNT pathway are activated by the binding of a WNT-protein ligand to a Frizzled family receptor (FZD). Wang et al. [13] showed that the DIXDC1 protein was induced upon WNT3A stimulation, whereas the DIXDC1 mRNA level was not significantly increased after WNT3A treatment. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FZD family along with DIXDC1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD8, DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1, DIXDC1-FZD2-FBXW4, DIXDC1-FZD2-LRP5, FZD5-DIXDC1-SEN2, DIXDC1-FSHB-FZD1, FZD5-DIXDC1-WNT2B, FZD5-CCND3-DIXDC1, DIXDC1-FZD2-PPP2CA, DIXDC1-FZD6-FZD8, DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD1, DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD8, DIXDC1-FZD2-LEF1, DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2, DIXDC1-FZD2-FZD7, DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT4, DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD8, DIXDC1-FZD2-TLE2, FZD5-DIXDC1-FRZB, DIXDC1-FGF4-FZD1, DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2B, DIXDC1-FZD2-SFRP4, DIXDC1-FOXN1-FZD7, DIXDC1-FZD2-TCF7 and DIXDC1-FZD2-WNT2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.6. Examining the behaviour of JUN-DIXDC1-X combinations

Wong et al. [14] investigated whether CCD1 could play a regulatory role in AXIN- and DVL-mediated JNK activation. c-JUN N-terminal kinases (JNKs) bind and phosphorylate c-JUN on Ser-63 and Ser-73 within its transcriptional activation domain. They show that CCD1 drastically inhibited JNK activation by both AXIN and DVL. Although DIX domains are sufficient for dimer formation between DVL and CCD1, CCD1 also required its coiled-coil domain for inhibition of JNK activation by DVL. DIXDC1 is the human homolog CCD1. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for JUN along with DIXDC1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1, DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1, DIXDC1-JUN-SLC9A3R1, DIXDC1-JUN-RHOA, DIXDC1-JUN-TLE1, DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4, DIXDC1-JUN-SEN2, DIXDC1-JUN-TLE2, DIXDC1-JUN-WNT2 and DIXDC1-JUN-WNT3A. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of DIXDC1 in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the DIXDC1, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

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Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For DIXDC1, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

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